

Plan-Driven Modeling Guidelines

Method: Plan-driven **Tools:** ChatGPT / Gemini (As assigned)

Case Study: Parking Lots / Baby Boom (As assigned)

Method Characteristics: Upfront planning, detailed documentation, and pre-defined, clear phases.

Task Overview: You are required to create a UML model for your assigned Case Study using the assigned tool and following the **Plan-driven** workflow defined below.

Required Artifacts:

1. **Use Case Diagram**
2. **Class Diagram**
3. **Sequence Diagram** (for the specific scenario defined in step 4 below)

General Instructions:

- **Systematic Workflow:** You must work systematically according to the phases detailed below.
- **Tool Interaction:** Use the assigned tool as much as possible. Conduct interactions where you evaluate the tool's outputs, request improvements or corrections, and repeat until you are satisfied with the result.
- **Manual Refinement:** If necessary, you may manually update the final artifacts (using PlantUML tools).
- **Language:** Interaction with the tool can be in English, Hebrew, or a mix, at your discretion.
- **Documentation:** Save the chat log in CSV format (using an export plugin) and provide a shared link to the chat.
- **Format:** Diagrams must be in **PlantUML** format. Ensure the tool provides valid syntax (starting with @startuml and ending with @enduml).
- **Submission:** Submit the final diagrams as .txt files and as image screenshots.

Work Phases

Phase 1: System Requirements Elicitation & Documentation

- Read the Case Study carefully.
- Identify the stakeholders and system goals.
- Extract functional and non-functional requirements.

Phase 2: Requirements Modeling

- Create a **Use Case Diagram** representing the interactions between actors and the system.
- Document the goal of each Use Case in a single sentence.

Phase 3: System Analysis

- Identify key domain concepts (Nouns = Classes, Verbs = Methods).
- Construct a **Class Diagram** including:
 - Classes with Attributes.
 - Required Methods.
 - Relationships between classes (associations, inheritance, etc.).

Phase 4: Behavior Modeling

- Create a **Sequence Diagram** describing the behavior for the specific scenario relevant to your case:
 - **For Parking Lots Case:** *Generating a Coupon Redemption Report for a Period.*
 - **For Baby Boom Case:** *Generating an Abnormal Examination Report for a Baby during a Period.*
- Verify consistency between the Sequence Diagram, the Use Case Diagram, and the Class Diagram; correct if necessary.